

INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS ON THE SURFACE QUALITY OF PRODUCTS MADE USING ARC ADDITIVE TECHNOLOGY WAAM (3D PRINTING)

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the study of the influence of the technological parameters of 3D arc printing (layer-by-layer cladding) of a fusible electrode (GMAW) on the quality of the surface and the mechanical properties of the resulting product. It was established that during additive arc welding of a fusible electrode, metal with almost identical mechanical properties in different directions (along and across the welded rolls) is formed in the created product, which corresponds to the structure of the cast metal. With a decrease in the driving energy from 150 to 40 J/mm, the productivity of the process decreases by more than half, while the quality of the surface formation improves, which is manifested in a decrease in its roughness from 160 to 110 μm . Productivity or speed of the process of 3D printing with a fusible electrode arc ((layer-by-layer cladding)) and the quality of the formed surface are mutually inverse parameters that can be used as optimization criteria when selecting the parameters of the process mode of such 3D printing (layer-by-layer cladding).

Keywords: additive cladding, arc with a fusible electrode, cladding rate, roughness, residual energy, residual stresses, mechanical properties.

Introduction

In recent years, significant progress has been made in the study of Wire-Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM) technology, where an electric arc of a fusible electrode burning in a shielding gas environment is used as a concentrated source of heating for the welding wire (GMAW) [1].

This technology of layer-by-layer growth of metal products is widely used in aerospace engineering, mechanical engineering, shipbuilding, medicine and other industries [2]. Compared to other additive methods, it has a number of advantages, such as significant energy efficiency (up to 90%) [3], high process productivity (2...8 kg/h and more) [4], relative simplicity and cheapness of equipment, no limitation on the size of manufactured products [5].

However, a number of issues related to the possible anisotropy of mechanical properties depending on the direction of growth, surface roughness, which sometimes forces the use of mechanical processing, etc., remain insufficiently researched.

In works [6-9], the authors studied the influence of various surfacing parameters on the appearance and stability of the molten metal bath formation, and in works [10-13] the influence of mode parameters on the structure and mechanical properties of steel products made of using additive technology. However, the influence of mode parameters on the quality of the surface of the finished additive product has not been practically studied.

Some researchers (for example, work [1]) note that the features of the formation of the geometric parameters of the rollers depending on the cooling conditions should not be the primary cause, but a consequence and a technological feature that should be taken into account in the manufacture of complex products.

Most of the studies (for example, works [8-12]) were performed under the conditions of multi-layer single-pass additive layer-by-layer cladding, with the aim of obtaining a tone-and-bone product of the "wall" type, but most often, to obtain volumetric products, it is necessary to apply multi-layer multi-pass cladding, which has certain differences from the single-pass.

In this regard, the **aim of the work** is to study the influence of the parameters of the multi-layer multi-pass additive cladding using an arc with a fusible electrode (GMAW) on the quality of the surface and on the mechanical properties of the products manufactured using this technology.

Research materials and methods

To conduct the experiment in the E. O. Paton Electric Welding Institute of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, we used a complex of equipment, which included: an AIR-50 industrial welding robot, a Fronius CMT 4000 Advanced welding power source, a robotic complex of welding equipment with Cold Metal Transfer (CMT) technology and a single-axis manipulator. Cladding was performed according to the technological scheme shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Technological scheme of robotic additive arc layer-by-layer cladding: 1 – nozzle-lo; 2 – shielding gas; 3 – the arc of the fusible electrode; 4 – a layer of deposited metal; 5 – electrode; 6 – welding bath; 7 – lining.

Development of the technological regimes of layer-by-layer cladding and growth of the "wall" was carried out on plates made of St3ps steel with dimensions of 250×100×8 mm using low-carbon welding wire ASKAYNAK SG-2 (ER70S-6) in an environment

of shielding gas CORGON 18 (82% Ar , 18% CO₂). The diameter of the wire was 1.0 mm, the value of the arc voltage was 14.5 V. Other parameters of the surfacing mode are given in Table 1.

Table 1.

Parameters of the surfacing mode.

No	Current strength, A	Wire feed speed, m/min	Cladding speed, cm/min	Running energy, J/mm
1	98	3,2	30	147,8
2	98	3,2	50	88,7
3	98	3,2	70	63,4
4	98	3,2	90	49,3
5	124	5,2	150	37,7

During the experiment, a "wall" consisting of 20 layers was formed layer by layer on the flat plates by longitudinal movement of the welding torch with an overlap of ~50% of the adjacent roller. The main criteria for choosing the surfacing mode were: high-quality

formation of the deposited metal (Fig. 2), stable arc burning at the lowest values of linear energy in the cladding process.

Fig. 2. Appearance of welded rollers.

Due to the fact that at low values of the welding current due to the instability of the arc process, it is often possible to obtain a defect in the form of non-fusion between the welded rollers, and at increased values there is an excessive accumulation of heat, the flow of molten metal and interruption of the process, the optimal surfacing mode. The reduction of heat cladding was carried out due to an increase in the cladding speed.

In order to obtain welded rollers of the same size and shape, after each layer was applied, it was cooled to a temperature of 120°C. Temperature control between applying layers was carried out with the help of a digital pyrometer model AMS-675.

The microrelief of the welded surface of Rz was studied on the obtained samples using a profilometer

model SRT 6200S (USA). The obtained results were transferred to a PC and processed in the software product "PowerGraph 3.3".

Then, on the regime that provided the least roughness of the surface, the walls were welded (Fig. 3), from which later samples were cut in the longitudinal and transverse directions for metallographic studies and determination of mechanical properties. Metallographic studies were performed on M400 («LECO», St. Joseph, MI, USA) microscope-microhardness tester. Tests of the mechanical properties of the deposited metal were carried out on the IR-100 breaking machine and the MK-30 A pendulum cutter. The hardness was measured using a HBT-5 (MICROTECH, Ukraine) Brinell hardness tester.

Fig. 3. Appearance of a welded "wall" made of low-carbon steel.

Research results

When the cladding speed is increased, a defect appears in the form of the formation of bumps and there are difficulties with the construction of the geometry (movement along a curve, circle, etc.).

It was established that with an increase in the cladding speed, there is a decrease in the linear energy and surface roughness of the sample (Fig. 4) as a result of a

decrease in the geometric characteristics of the rollers (Fig. 5).

Thus, with an increase in the cladding speed from 30 to 90 cm/min, the linear energy decreases by three times, while the roughness decreases by 30 units of Rz or by 20% (Fig. 4), and with an increase in the linear energy from 40 to 150 J/mm roughness increases almost one and a half times (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4.

The influence of the cladding speed on the value of the linear energy and the roughness of the wall surface.

Fig. 5. Dependence of the roughness of the surface and the dimensions of the roller on the value of the linear energy of the process.

At the same time, the microstructure of the deposited samples corresponds to the structure of the cast metal (Fig. 6).

When studying the properties of the deposited metal, it was found that when the samples are stretched,

stresses occur in them, which are similar in magnitude regardless of the direction of their cutting from the deposited wall, and the deviation of the values is within the measurement error (Fig. 7).

Fig. 6. Microstructure of deposited samples, $\times 100$.

Fig. 7. Dependence of stress on the elongation of samples cut along (1) and across (2) the cladding tracks.

The mechanical properties of the deposited metal (strengths σ_B and σ_T) are at the level of hot-rolled steel, and plastic properties (δ) even exceed this indicator (Table 2).

Table 2.

Mechanical properties of the deposited metal.

Material	Direction of sample cutting	Strength limit σ_B , MPa	Yield strength $\sigma_{0,2}$, MPa	Relative elongation δ , %
ASKAYNAK SG-2 (ER70S-6)	longitudinal	508	370	34
	transverse	476	332	30
	average value	492	351	32
steel 09G2S (hot-rolled sheet)	-	490	345	21

Conclusions

1. During additive arc welding of a fusible electrode, metal with almost identical mechanical properties in different directions (along and across the welded rolls) is formed in the product, which corresponds to the structure of the cast metal.

2. With a decrease in the driving energy from 150 to 40 J/mm, the productivity of the process decreases by more than half, while the quality of the surface formation improves, which is manifested in a decrease in its roughness from 160 to 110 μm .

3. Productivity or speed of the process of 3D printing (layer-by-layer cladding) with a fusible electrode arc and the quality of the formed surface are mutually inverse parameters that can be used as optimization criteria when selecting the parameters of the process mode of such 3D printing.

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